

SAJPCI

Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues (SAJPCI)

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The Editor-in-Chief

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Untangling the Mind Behind Bars: How Emotion Regulation Connects Self-Efficacy, Guilt-Induced Depression, and Suicidal Ideation in Ilorin Correctional Facility

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Abstract

In correctional facilities, where psychological distress is exacerbated by incarceration-related stressors like guilt, loss of autonomy, and impaired emotional functioning, suicide is still a serious public health concern. Anchored on social cognitive and emotion regulation frameworks, this study investigated how emotion regulation links perceived self-efficacy and guilt-induced depression to suicidal ideation among inmates in Ilorin Correctional Facility, Nigeria. A cross-sectional ex post facto survey design was employed. Purposive sampling was used to choose 210 inmates from Oke Kura Correctional Center in Ilorin (mean age = 37.3 years; 92.4% male). Perceived self-efficacy, guilt-induced depression, emotion regulation, and suicidal ideation were evaluated using standardized tools. Data were analysed using Pearson correlation, multiple regression, and mediation analysis. Suicidal ideation was found to be jointly and independently predicted by perceived self-efficacy and depression brought on by guilt, which together accounted for 63.4% of the variance in suicidal ideation. Suicidal ideation was strongly positively correlated with guilt-induced depression, whereas suicidal ideation was significantly decreased by perceived self-efficacy. The relationship between suicidal ideation and guilt-induced depression was not mediated by emotion regulation, according to mediation analysis. The relationship between perceived self-efficacy and suicidal ideation was, however, significantly mediated by emotion regulation. These findings highlight the significance of incorporating guilt-focused therapeutic interventions, emotion regulation programs and training, and self-efficacy enhancement into correctional mental health and rehabilitation programs in order to lower the risk of inmate suicide.

Keywords: Suicidal ideation, Guilt-induced depression, Self-efficacy, Emotion regulation, Prison inmates, Nigeria

Introduction

Suicide continues to be one of the most urgent global public health issues, accounting for nearly a million deaths each year and being one of the leading causes of death globally, especially among young and middle-aged adults (WHO, 2016). Suicide rates have alarmingly increased in both developed and developing countries over the past few decades, spanning age, gender, and socioeconomic status (Gong et al., 2011; Seghatoleslam et al., 2010). Biological vulnerability, psychological distress, social adversity, and contextual stressors interact to shape the complex and multifaceted phenomenon of suicidal behavior, which is defined as intentional acts or thoughts aimed at ending one's life (Krug et al., 2002). Although physical health risks like infectious diseases, malnutrition, and accidents have received more attention, the psychological factors of suicide, particularly among incarcerated populations, remain inadequately addressed.

People who are incarcerated are one group that has a disproportionately high risk of suicide. Suicide is one of the most common causes of death in correctional facilities, with rates several times higher than those in the general population, according to epidemiological evidence (Fazel et al., 2010; Adrian et al., 2024). Prison suicide rates vary from 24 to 89 per 100,000 person years across several jurisdictions, indicating a global trend of increased vulnerability among prisoners. According to studies, between 19% and 22% of prisoners report having attempted suicide at some point in their lives (Favril et al., 2020a), and prevalence estimates of suicidal ideation among inmates in low- and middle-income countries range from 20% to over 40%. (Tadesse et al., 2021; Adewuya et al., 2021).

Correctional facilities in Nigeria reflect this worldwide reality. According to reports, Nigeria's national suicide rate is estimated to be around 17 per 100,000 people, indicating a rising and serious suicide burden (WHO, 2016). The psychological well-being of inmates in Nigerian correctional facilities is severely compromised by overcrowding, extended pre-trial detention, poor healthcare services, social isolation, and exposure to ongoing stressors (Awopetu, 2014; Okeke et al., 2020).

According to the Stress–Diathesis framework of suicide and the Cry of Pain Model (Williams, 2001), these circumstances firmly established feelings of helplessness, hopelessness, and entrapment—core psychological states strongly linked to suicidal ideation. (Mann et al., 1999). If the psychological processes underlying suicidal ideation in Nigerian prisons are not thoroughly investigated, there is a chance that avoidable deaths will continue, rehabilitation

objectives will be compromised, and the system's evidence-based mental health policies will be weakened. Guilt-induced depression is a significant psychological process that is essential to suicide risk.

In correctional settings, this merits special attention. Guilt is a self-conscious moral feeling that arises from the belief that one has transgressed social or personal norms. It is usually accompanied by regret, remorse, self-blame, and a desire for atonement. Dearing and Tangney (2002). Because inmates in correctional facilities must deal with the repercussions of their actions on a daily basis, being separated from loved ones, and perceived moral failure, incarceration itself frequently exacerbates guilt.

Unmanaged, unresolved, and internalized guilt can result in a depressive cognitive affective state known as "guilt-induced depression," which is characterized by persistent self-loathing, worthlessness, and hopelessness. This conceptualization is consistent with Beck's Cognitive Theory of Depression, which highlights excessive self-blame, negative self-appraisals, and maladaptive self-schemas as key symptoms of depression (Beck, 1967). The crucial role that guilt plays in suicidal processes is supported by empirical data. Research on combat veterans has demonstrated that guilt is a powerful predictor of suicidal ideation and attempts, even after adjusting for depression and symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder. Orbach (1997) identified guilt as a core affective state among suicidal individuals. (Hendin & Haas, 1991; McLean et al., 2012).

Guilt can become chronic and psychologically toxic in correctional facilities, where there are few opportunities for reparative action and a high level of stigmatization. This increases the risk of depression and suicidal thoughts. Despite its obvious contextual relevance, guilt-induced depression among Nigerian prisoners is still poorly understood, under researched, and empirically understudied. Perceived self-efficacy, which is accurately defined as a person's belief in their ability to exert control over life events and successfully manage challenging situations, is another significant psychological factor influencing the mental health of prisoners (Bandura, 2005). Self-efficacy influences how people perceive stressors, control their emotions, and persevere in the face of difficulty, according to the Social Cognitive Theory. Inmates' sense of competence and control is frequently undermined by incarceration, which severely restricts autonomy and personal agency. In a variety of populations, low perceived self-efficacy has been associated with suicidal thoughts, depression, increased emotional distress, and maladaptive coping mechanisms (Fagbenro & Olagundoye, 2019; Li et al., 2024).

On the other hand, even in extremely restrictive settings, high self-efficacy serves as a psychological resource that reduces stress, builds resilience, and improves adaptive coping. An important explanatory link between suicidal thoughts, guilt-induced depression, and self-efficacy is emotion regulation. The processes by which people keep an eye on, assess, and adjust their emotional experiences in response to situational demands are referred to as emotion regulation (Gross, 1998). Emotional regulation demands are increased in correctional facilities because of ongoing stress, social deprivation, and restricted access to helpful coping mechanisms. Depression, self-harm, and suicidal thoughts have all been strongly linked to deficiencies in emotion regulation, including low emotional awareness, trouble controlling impulses, and a dependence on maladaptive coping mechanisms like suppression (Norouzi, 2025; Ogbonnaya et al., 2024).

Theoretically, self-efficacy affects psychological outcomes through emotion regulation, which functions as a mediating mechanism. Higher self-efficacy individuals are more likely to employ or manage adaptive emotion regulation techniques like cognitive reappraisal, which lessens the influence of depressive and guilty emotions on suicidal thoughts (Li et al., 2025; Chukwuemeka & Obi Nwosu, 2021). Low self-efficacy, on the other hand, undermines self-assurance in handling emotional distress, leading to a greater dependence on maladaptive regulation techniques and an increase in depressive symptoms brought on by guilt. This path was consistent with the Interpersonal Psychological Theory of Suicide (Joiner, 2005), which holds that suicidal desire is influenced by ongoing psychological suffering and despair, especially when people feel burdened and emotionally trapped.

There is still a startling lack of empirical research analyzing the connections between suicidal ideation, depression, emotion regulation, and self-efficacy in Nigerian prisons, despite mounting evidence from around the world. Inadequate mental health interventions, missed opportunities for early identification of at-risk inmates, and a continued reliance on punitive rather than rehabilitative correctional practices are just a few of the far-reaching clinical and policy ramifications of the incapacity or failure to look into these psychological mechanisms. It is therefore essential to comprehend how guilt-induced depression and perceived self-efficacy interact through emotion regulation to impact suicidal ideation in order to develop culturally appropriate screening instruments, psychological treatments, and mental health policies in Nigerian correctional facilities. Therefore, by investigating the mediating role of emotion regulation in the relationship between perceived self-efficacy, guilt-induced depression, and suicidal ideation among inmates at Ilorin correctional facility, the current study

aims to close a significant knowledge gap. Based on well-established psychological theories and contextualized within the lived realities of incarceration, the study intends to contribute empirically and practically to evidence-based correctional mental health policy, inmate rehabilitation, and suicide prevention in Nigeria.

Hypotheses

1. Perceived guilt-induced depression and perceived self-efficacy will jointly and independently predict suicidal ideation
2. The association between perceived guilt-induced and suicidal ideation will be considerably mediated by emotion regulation.
3. The association between suicidal ideation and perceived self-efficacy will be mediated by emotion regulation.

Methods

Design

A cross-sectional, survey design was used to gather information on prison inmates' perceived guilt-induced depression, perceived self-efficacy, emotion regulation, and suicidal ideation in Ilorin correctional facilities. Suicidal ideation was the criterion variable, emotion regulation was the mediating variable, and the predictor variables were perceived self-efficacy and guilt-induced depression. The expo facto method was chosen because the researcher wanted to measure the relationships between these variables without altering them. Additionally, this design was deemed the most suitable due to its ability to provide guidance on the relationship between the variables of interest. The researcher collected data from the correctional facilities in a timely manner using this method.

Setting

The research setting is Oke Kura Correctional Center (formerly Oke Kura Prison) in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria, on Oke Kura Road, close to the Emir's Palace. It's one of the state's oldest prisons, it was first constructed during the colonial era. The Federal Ministry of Interior's Nigerian Correctional Service (NCoS) is in charge of running it. Its medium-security inmate population and capacity range from 120 to 150. As a result, Oke Kura frequently houses between 300 and 400 prisoners, meaning the facility runs at more than twice its capacity, according to reports and inspections by the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) and media outlets. Both convicted and awaiting-trial inmates (ATPs) are overwhelmingly male in terms of demographics.

Participants

Two hundred inmates were chosen from Oke Kura correctional facility in Ilorin using purposive sampling techniques. The respondents' age group of 39–48 years old accounted for the largest percentage of prisoners (36.67%), an indication that it's the most prevalent group in the study. The next age range to the previous one is 29 to 38 years old, which account for 30.00% of the total population. Having a 21.43% of the entire population between the ages of 19 and 28 means a significant number of young adults are incarcerated. Conversely, only 0.48% (1 respondent) were 59 years of age or older, and 11.43% of the respondents were between the ages of 49 and 58. The respondents' gender distribution was noticeably skewed. Only 16 (7.6%) of the 210 prisoners in the sample were female, compared to 194 (92.4%) who were male. Regarding religious affiliation, the majority of respondents (130, or 61.9%) identified as Christian, and 80, or 38.1%, identified as Muslim. The inmate population sampled in this study is mainly made up of men in their productive adult years, with a balanced representation of the two main religions in Nigeria, according to the socio-demographic data, in conclusion.

Inclusion Criteria and Exclusion Criteria

Participants in this study were inmates who fulfilled the following requirements: The registered inmate in an Ilorin correctional facility who is mentally stable, able to understand and react to inquiries, and, most importantly, willing to participate willingly and give informed consent. Inmates registered in correctional facilities outside of Ilorin and those with severe psychiatric disorders that affect their cognitive function were not included in the study.

Ethical Considerations

Participants' ethical protection received special attention because suicide-related research is sensitive. Participants were informed that certain questions on the questionnaire could cause psychological or emotional distress. Prior to data collection, all participants received a clear explanation in a language they could comprehend of the study's purpose, objectives, research procedures, anticipated duration, and nature of the assessment instruments. The rights of participants, such as the right to voluntary participation and the freedom to decline or leave the study at any time without facing penalties, coercion, or negative outcomes, were made abundantly evident to them. Strict confidentiality was upheld; all answers were used only for research, and no identifying information was written on the questionnaires.

Participants were assured that if participation caused emotional distress, the correctional health unit would provide appropriate psychological support, even though no physical risk was anticipated. Beyond the minimal risk associated with self-report measures, there was no legal, physical, or psychological harm associated with participating in the study. After a thorough evaluation of the research protocol, the University Institutional Ethical Review Board (IERB) granted ethical approval for the study. Prior to data collection, permission was also obtained from the relevant correctional authorities. The research procedure was approved by the university's Institutional Ethical Review Board (IERB) following a thorough ethical review.

Instruments

Four standardized psychological tests are used in this study to assess suicidal thoughts, emotion regulation, perceived guilt-induced depression, and perceived self-efficacy. These tools have been used extensively in psychological research to evaluate the constructs that are pertinent to this investigation. Each of the questionnaire's five (5) sections asks for information on relevant variables.

Section A: The participant demographics was included in this section. Details like participant's gender, age, and religion are included in the demographic section.

Section B: General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES – 10 Items)

Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995) created the 10-item Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES), a widely recognized and psychometrically sound measure that gauges an individual's hopeful belief in their ability to handle a variety of challenging circumstances. Higher scores indicate greater perceived self-efficacy. Each item is rated on a 4-point Likert scale, where 1 represents not at all true and 4 represents exactly true. According to EFA and CFA, the GSES is thought to have a unidimensional factor structure, meaning that each item measures a single underlying construct of generalized self-efficacy. The scale's internal consistency reliability ranges from 0.80 to 0.90, which is generally considered to reflect strong psychometric qualities.

Section C: Adapted Beck Depression Inventory- Short Form (BDI-SF – 13 Items)

The 13-item self-report tool known as the adapted Beck Depression Inventory–Short Form (BDI-SF), that is based on the original 21-item BDI, is intended to evaluate depressive symptomatology during the previous two weeks. In order to indicate increasing degrees of

severity, items are rated on a four-point scale from 0 to 3. More severe depression is indicated by higher scores. Sadness, self-dislike, indecision, and exhaustion are some of the major symptoms of depression that are addressed by each item. A unidimensional structure is generally supported by factor analyses (EFA and CFA), indicating that the BDI-SF assesses a single underlying construct of depression severity. Nonetheless, a two-factor solution that represents both somatic-performance and cognitive-affective symptoms has been reported in some studies. Cronbach's alpha values range from 0.80 to 0.90, indicating high internal consistency.

Section D: Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ – 10 Items)

The 10-item ERQ, created by Gross and John (2003), evaluates two aspects of emotion regulation: Expressive Suppression (4 items) and Cognitive Reappraisal (6 items). Higher scores indicate a greater propensity to employ that emotion regulation technique. Items are scored on a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 represents strongly disagree and 7 represents strongly agree. The two main emotion regulation techniques are the focus of the 10-item version. 1 Cognitive Reappraisal (6 items): this type of cognitive-emotional regulation entails altering one's perspective on a situation for the purpose of changing its emotional impact and another technique for controlling emotions is expressive suppression, which consists of limiting or suppressing outward displays of emotion. Both exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) supported the ERQ's intended two-factor structure. The expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal scales both show strong reliability. Strong alpha and omega coefficients, which are typically ≥ 0.75 , support reliability.

Section E: Modified Scale for Suicidal Ideation

This scale is a self-report or clinician-administered instrument used to gauge the intensity and seriousness of suicidal thoughts. Higher scores indicate more severe suicidal thoughts. The scale consists of 18 items that are rated on a four-point scale (0–3). It contains sub themes such as preparation, deterrents, and a desire to die, the MSSSI highlights the frequency and severity of suicidal thoughts. With Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega values ≥ 0.85 , MSSSI showed outstanding internal consistency.

Results

Test of Relationships among the Study Variables

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Matrix showing the Means, SD and relationships among the variables in the study (N = 210)

	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I. Age	37.3	9.62	–						
II. Gender	1.08	.27	-.214**	–					
III. Religion	1.38	.49	-.392**	.070	–				
IV. PSE	26.67	7.42	-.355**	.088	.204**	–			
V. PGID	11.30	6.77	.122	-.042	.036	-.406**	–		
VI. ER	52.47	11.45	.124	-.130	-.231**	.507**	-.293**	–	
VII. SI	13.93	8.63	-.100	.038	.276**	.061	.701**	-.258**	–

PSE: Perceived self-efficacy, PGID: Perceived guilt-induced depression, ER: Emotion regulation, SI: Suicidal ideation **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to Table 1 findings, there was no correlation between age and suicidal thoughts ($r(208) = -.10$). The correlation was not statistically significant ($p > .05$). Suicidal ideation and gender had a weak but positive correlation ($r(208) = .04$), but this relationship was not statistically significant ($p > .05$). Suicidal ideation and religion had a significant and positive correlation ($r(208) = .28, p < .01$).

This suggests that there is a significant correlation between suicidal ideation and an inmate's religious affiliation. The results showed a significant inverse correlation between PSE & PGI ($r(208) = -.406, p < .001$) and that guilt-induced depression was less common in those with high self-efficacy. Higher levels of guilt-induced depression were linked to higher levels of suicidal ideation, according to a significant positive correlation between PGI and SI ($r(208) = .701, p < .001$). The non-significant correlation between PSE and SI ($r(208) = -.061, p = .382$) indicates that there was no significant linear relationship between suicidal ideation and perceived self-efficacy. The General Self-Efficacy Scale (range = 10–40) was used to gauge perceived self-efficacy. A moderate degree of perceived competence among prisoners is indicated by the observed mean score ($M = 26.67, SD = 7.42$), which is slightly above the scale midpoint (25). As would be expected in correctional populations with varying offence histories, sentence statuses, and psychosocial resources, the comparatively large standard deviation suggests significant variability in perceived agency. The adapted Beck Depression Inventory

Short Form (range = 0–39) was used to measure perceived guilt-induced depression; the mean score ($M = 11.30$, $SD = 6.77$), consistent with previous research on incarcerated populations, indicates mild to moderate depressive symptom severity. Individual variations in the internalization of guilt, moral self-evaluation, and coping mechanisms are reflected in the observed and documented dispersion.

The Emotion Regulation Questionnaire, which measures emotion regulation (range = 10–70), produced a mean score of 52.47 ($SD = 11.45$), indicating a moderate level of emotion regulation practice. The wide range highlights the disparities in inmates' emotional coping styles, as the ERQ measures both maladaptive (expressive suppression) and adaptive (cognitive reappraisal) strategies. The Modified Scale for Suicidal Ideation (range = 0–54) was used to measure suicidal ideation. Instead of temporary distress, the mean score ($M = 13.93$, $SD = 8.63$) indicates the presence of clinically significant suicidal ideation. The criterion validity of suicidal ideation as the outcome variable is supported by the comparatively high standard deviation, which points to a subgroup of prisoners at notably elevated risk of suicide.

Predictive Impact of Self-Efficacy and Depression Induced by Perceived Guilt on Suicidal ideations. To examine the combined and separate contributions of perceived self-efficacy and depression brought on by guilt to suicidal thoughts, multiple regression analysis was performed.

The overall model was statistically significant, $F(2, 207) = 179.07$, $p < .001$, explaining 63.4% of the variance in suicidal ideation ($R^2 = .634$).

Table 2: Multiple Regression Table displaying Independent and Joint determinant of perceived guilt-induced depression and perceived self-efficacy on Suicidal Ideation among prison inmates in Ilorin metropolis

Variable	β	SE	95% CI	<i>B</i>	<i>p</i>
Constant	-11.390	1.838	[-15.013, 7.767]	-	<.001
Perceived guilt-induced depression	.480	.054	[.375, .586]	.413	<.001
Perceived self-efficacy	1.107	.059	[.991, 1.222]	.868	<.001

Note. $R^2 = .634$, $F(2, 207) = 179.067$, $p < 0.01$

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to determine the independent and joint predictive effects of depression caused by guilt and perceived self-efficacy on suicidal ideation among inmates in Ilorin correctional facilities. Table 2 displays the findings. The overall statistical significance of the model was demonstrated by $F(2, 207) = 179.067$, $p < .001$, and an R^2 value of .634. This suggests that depression caused by guilt and perceived self-efficacy together explained roughly 63.4% of the variation in suicidal ideation. Suicidal ideation was significantly predicted by depression caused by perceived guilt-induced depression, according to a subsequent analysis of the independent effects ($\beta = .413$, $B = .480$, $SE = .054$, 95% CI [.375, .586], $p < .001$). This finding shows that inmates who experience higher levels of guilt-induced depression are more likely to consider suicide.

Perceived self-efficacy was found to be a significant independent predictor of suicidal ideation ($\beta = .868$, $t = 18.87$, $p < .001$). Similarly, inmates' confidence in their ability to manage challenges is a critical factor in reducing suicidal ideation. These results show that both perceived self-efficacy and guilt-induced depression significantly and independently predict suicidal ideation, and when combined, they account for a significant portion of the variation in suicidal ideation among inmates. The hypothesis is thus accepted. Suicidal ideation was significantly predicted by perceived guilt-induced depression ($B = 0.480$, $SE = 0.054$, $\beta =$

0.413, $p < .001$), suggesting that higher levels of depressive symptoms related to guilt were linked to more suicidal thoughts.

Evidently, perceived self-efficacy also became a significant independent predictor ($B = 1.107$, $SE = 0.059$, $\beta = 0.868$, $p < .001$). Since unstandardized coefficients are scale-dependent, even though the unstandardized coefficient is greater than 1, this does not go against the regression assumptions. Because the suicidal ideation measure and the General Self-Efficacy Scale use different metric ranges, coefficients larger than 1 are statistically acceptable. Crucially, a suppression effect is suggested by the difference between the significant regression coefficient and the non-significant zero-order correlation. Perceived self-efficacy reveals its latent protective function that is hidden at the bivariate level, explaining unique variance in suicidal ideation when guilt-induced depression is controlled.

Table 3: Mediation Analysis Summary for the Effect of Perceived Guilt-Induced Depression on Suicidal Ideation via Emotion Regulation

Path	B	SE	R ²	t	P	LLCI	ULCI
X → M(a)	-.49	.11	.08	-4.42	<.01	-.71	-.27
M → Y(b)	-.04	.03	—	-1.11	.26	-.12	0.03
X → Y(c')	.87	.06	.49	-13.23	<.01	.74	1.01
Indirect	.02	.01	—	—	—	-.008	.058

Effect (a*b)

X = Perceived guilt-induced depression, Y = Suicidal ideation, M = Emotion regulation.

To determine if emotion regulation mediates the link between perceived guilt induced depression and suicidal ideation, a mediation analysis was also carried out. Table 3 provides a summary of the findings. Emotion regulation was significantly predicted by perceived guilt-induced depression ($\beta = -0.496$, $SE = 0.112$, $t(208) = -4.42$, $p < .001$), suggesting that there was a relationship between worse emotion regulation and higher levels of guilt-induced depression. Suicidal ideation, however, was not significantly predicted by emotion regulation ($\beta = -0.043$, $SE = 0.039$, $t(207) = -1.11$, $p = .268$). Perceived guilt-induced depression continued to have a strong and statistically significant direct effect on suicidal ideation ($\beta = 0.872$, $SE = 0.066$, $t(207) = 13.23$, $p < .001$), indicating that suicidal ideation are strongly impacted by guilt-induced depressive feelings. Since zero was included in the confidence interval, the indirect effect

through emotion regulation ($\beta = 0.021$, $SE = 0.016$, 95% CI [-0.009, 0.058]) was not significant. Consequently, the association between perceived guilt-induced depression and suicidal ideations was not mediated by emotion regulation. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4: Mediation Analysis Summary for the Effect of Perceived Self-Efficacy on Suicidal Ideation via Emotion Regulation

Path	B	SE	R ²	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
X → M(a)	.78	.09	.25	8.49	<.01	.60	.96
M → Y(b)	-.29	.05	—	-5.12	<.01	-.40	-.18
X → Y(c')	.30	.08	.11	3.40	<.01	.12	.47
Indirect	-.23	.04	—	—	—	-.33	-.14

Effect (a*b)

X = Perceived self-efficacy, Y = Suicidal ideation, M = Emotion regulation.

The mediation analysis examined the indirect relationship between suicidal ideation and perceived self-efficacy through emotion regulation. The findings demonstrated that emotion regulation was significantly and favorably predicted by self-efficacy ($B = 0.783$, $SE = 0.092$, $t = 8.493$, $p < .001$), indicating that individuals with higher self-efficacy have better emotional control abilities. Perceived self-efficacy accounted for about 25.8% of the variation in emotion regulation ($R^2 = 0.258$). Emotion regulation significantly and negatively predicted suicidal ideation ($B = -0.293$, $SE = 0.057$, $t = -5.127$, $p < .001$), suggesting that individuals with strong emotional regulation skills are less likely to experience suicidal ideation. The direct correlation between suicidal ideation and self-efficacy remained significant even after controlling for emotion regulation. ($B = 0.300$, $SE = 0.088$, $t = 3.400$, $p < .001$, $R^2 = 0.116$). The presence of the positive coefficient indicates that self-efficacy continues to have an impact even after emotion regulation has been accounted for. Self-efficacy had a significant indirect effect on suicidal ideation through emotion regulation ($B = -0.230$, $SE = 0.047$, 95% CI [-0.330, -0.145]). Emotion regulation was confirmed as a significant mediator since the confidence interval excluded zero. These results suggest that increased self-efficacy enhances emotion regulation, which in turn reduced suicidal ideation. This suggests the protective role of self-efficacy and

emotion regulation at reducing suicidal ideations among individuals. Therefore, the hypothesis was accepted.

Discussion

The present study provides evidence for two distinct psychological pathways underlying suicidal ideation among incarcerated individuals.

Firstly, guilt-induced depression exerted a strong and direct effect on suicidal ideation. This result in hypothesis one is consistent with the previous findings that combat-related guilt was the most significant predictor of suicidal ideation and suicide attempts among Vietnam combat veterans (Hendin & Haas, 1991, and that guilt induced depression was significantly correlated with suicidal ideation in a clinical sample of Iraq and Afghanistan combat veterans with combat-related PTSD (McLean et al., 2012).and such it was accepted. The best way to interpret this finding is in the context of Beck's Cognitive Theory of Depression, which holds that hopelessness—a key factor in suicidal thoughts—is fostered by ongoing self-blame and negative self-schemas. Guilt is frequently persistent and morally complex in correctional settings, reflecting perceived violations of deeply held social and personal values. Since such guilt functions at an existential and moral level rather than a purely affective one, it is less amenable to modulation through emotion regulation techniques. This explains why this relationship could not be mediated by emotion regulation. This pattern is also consistent with the Cry of Pain Model, which amplifies suicidal desire by using guilt as a symbol of perceived defeat, imprisonment as a symbol of entrapment, and few opportunities for moral repair as a means of eliminating perceived rescue.

Second, even though correlation results did not show a significant direct relationship, regression analysis revealed that self-efficacy was a negative predictor of suicidal ideation. Suicidal thoughts were not prevalent among prisoners who believe they have a high degree of self-efficacy and are capable of overcoming obstacles in life. This outcome is in line with research by Li et al. (2024), who studied 2,051 adults in Jiangsu Province, China, and discovered that low self-efficacy leads to unhealthy coping strategies like contemplation, avoidance, or suicidal thoughts. In a similar vein, the study's results support those of Fagbenro & Olagundoye (2019), who discovered that low self-efficacy raises the risk of suicidal thoughts. This is significant because self-efficacy serves as a psychological buffer in trying circumstances. As a result, the hypothesis was approved. According to Social Cognitive Theory, people who have higher levels of self-efficacy are more

likely to use adaptive regulation techniques like cognitive reappraisal because they feel more confident in their capacity to handle emotional distress. Internal beliefs about competence become crucial for emotional stability in the constrictive prison environment where there is little external control. Suicidal thoughts and psychological suffering are subsequently decreased by effective emotion regulation.

Despite this, the mediation indicates that emotion regulation did not significantly predict suicidal ideation. This suggests that self-blame, hopelessness, and despair, rather than emotion regulation, are the ways in which guilt influences suicidal ideation. The results of Li et al. (2025) are supported by this. According to Ogbonnaya et al. (2024), adaptive emotion regulation techniques like cognitive reappraisal mediated the protective effect of mindfulness on suicidal thoughts. They also discovered that maladaptive techniques like expressive suppression partially mediated the influence of perceived burdensomeness and fear of negative evaluation on suicidal ideation, while cognitive reappraisal mitigated these effects.

Additionally, the results of this study are in line with those of Spitzzen et al. (2020), who discovered that emotional avoidance acted as a partial mediator between increased suicidal ideation and non-suicidal self-injury and lower emotion regulation self-efficacy. The findings of Zhang et al. (2022), which demonstrated that regulatory emotional self-efficacy significantly reduced psychological distress, are also supported by the results of this study. These findings highlight the importance of developing confidence in managing emotions to prevent depression and suicidal thoughts.

In summary, the findings point to two distinct psychological pathways: first, guilt-induced depression directly increases suicidal ideation, whereas self-efficacy indirectly reduces suicidal ideation by improving emotion regulation.

This demonstrates the need for prison-based intervention programs that include guilt resolution, emotional regulation training, and self-efficacy development in order to effectively reduce suicidal behavior among inmates.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has shown that perceived guilt-induced depression and perceived self-efficacy had combined effect on suicidal ideation in prison inmates. The fact that there was a correlation between suicidal ideation and guilt-induced depression shows how unresolved guilt in incarceration could impact life. However, suicidal ideation was negatively predicted by

self-efficacy and emotion regulation mediated this effect, showing the importance of emotion in reducing the risk of suicide. Though the relationship between guilt-induced depression and suicidal ideation was never mediated by emotion regulation, meaning the guilt may require a holistic therapeutic approaches than emotion regulation strategies. The results reveal that emotion control, self-efficacy and guilt-induce depression interact in a complex way to shape suicidal ideation. Without any doubt, this study has added to the growing body of knowledge in addressing the risk factors in suicidal ideation which in turn necessitated the need for focused, comprehensive mental health interventions in correctional facilities.

Recommendation

The result of this study attempts to provide some methodological and practical recommendations that may help the future researchers in various aspects. Therefore, it's recommended that there should be implementation of self-efficacy development programs with intent of assisting inmates develop coping mechanisms and confidence through life skills training. Secondly, prison authority should as a matter of necessity promote psychosocial support initiatives for the inmates. In addition, healthy coping mechanism should equally be encouraged. In other to address issues of stress management, control inmate's emotions, and teach cognitive restructuring, the prison authorities should factor emotion regulation training in their rehabilitation programme. Additionally, early identification of inmates with high guilt or low self-efficacy is important for proper intervention program through routine mental health screening, particularly at intake. Doing this will enhance adjustment to the prison environment and reduce guilt thereby preserving mental stability of the inmates. Suicidal ideation would have drastically reduced when efforts to establish a more encouraging correctional facilities environment that places an emphasis on inmates' mental health, emotional stability, and long-term rehabilitation are put in place.

Limitation and Suggestion for Future Studies

The study had a number of shortcomings, even though its research hypotheses were accepted and offered discerning information about the mediating role emotion regulation and how perceived guilt-induced depression and perceived self-efficacy predicted suicidal. The primary limitation was the use of self-reported data obtained through questionnaires. This method may not always give room for complete honesty because participants' responses could be influenced by inaccurate self-evaluation. In order to address this limitation and gain more comprehensive

understanding of the mediating role of emotion regulation in the prediction of suicidal ideation by guilt induced depression, future research should consider using other forms of data collection techniques, such as observational studies and interviews.

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